

**POPULATION STATUS OF CRITICALLY ENDANGERED MEDICINAL PLANT
“*COMMIPHORA WIGHTII* (ARN.) BHANDARI” AT KHUND MALIR, HINGOL
NATIONAL PARK, BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN**

Saeed ul Islam^{*1}, Dr Muhammad Sajjad², Rab Nawaz³, Muhammad Moazzam⁴

sislam@wwf.org.pk

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18861185>

Keywords

Population status, *Commiphora wightii*, Critically Endangered, Conservation, Hingol National Park, Balochistan.

Article History

Received: 29 December 2025

Accepted: 13 February 2026

Published: 28 February 2026

Copyright @Author

Corresponding Author: *

Saeed ul Islam

Abstract

According to the vegetation assessment, total of 11 samples was collected by using random transect method, to assess species dominancy by multiple calculations including frequency, relative frequency, cover, related cover and important value index (IVI). The results reveals that *Commiphora wightii* is highly dominated species with the SDR value of 46.3 which is almost half of the total cover of the associated species in the study area, the second dominated species with the SDR value of 12.3 was *Inula grantioides* belongs to family Asteraceae, the reason for their dominancy is its strong aroma which prevent it from grazing, the third dominant species was exotic and invasive species *Prosopis juliflora* with the SDR value of 8.57. Population of *Commiphora wightii* facing several threats at Kund Malir, Hingol National Park, including overgrazing, unsustainable exploitation and severe drought, if conservation initiatives has not been taken it may locally be extinct from the park.

Introduction: Indian bdellium (*Commiphora wightii*), (syn. *Commiphora mukul*) locally known as ‘Guggul’ is thorny and densely branched shrub, pleasant aroma with papery bark texture, sessile alternate leaves and dimorphic flowers, the slow growing plant takes about 8-10 to attains a height of about three meters (Mishra and Kumar, 2010), belongs to the family Burseraceae. The genus has 185 species found in tropical and sub-tropical areas of the world including east and southern Africa, Arabia, Pakistan and India (Khan, 1958; Choudhary, 1959; Hooker, 1872; Nasir and Ali, 1972; Atal *et al.*, 1975; Gupta *et al.*, 1996; Soni, 2010; Sharma & Kumar, 2012). High diversity of the genus has recorded from east Africa and Somalia (Khan, 1958; Vander Walt, 1974, 1975; Vollesen, 1989; Thulin, 2000; Hanus *et al.*, 2005;

Kant *et al.*, 2010). Of these only two species *Commiphora stocksiana* and *C. wightii* are reported from Pakistan (Jafri, 1966; Nasir and Ali, 1972). The plan has highly medicinal values having hypocholesterolaemic, hypolipidaemic, anti-arthritic, anti-bacterial, anti-oxidantal, anti-malarial, anti-schistomal, anti-microbial, muscle relaxing, larvicidal, mollucidal, lipid regulating, strong purifying and rejuvenating properties, reports said that the plant is used from last 3000 years in Ayurvedic medicines (Kirtikar and Basu, 1935; Chakravarty, 1975; Joshi, 1980; Kumar and Shankar, 1982; Satyavati, 1990; Claeson *et al.*, 1991; Hocking, 1993; Allam *et al.*, 2001; Massoud *et al.*, 2001, 2004; Francis *et al.*, 2004; Wang *et al.*, 2004; Abbas *et al.*, 2007; Shen *et al.*, 2007; Goyal *et al.*, 2011). Commercial gum

tapping is one of the serious issues for the population decline in the study area as well as various parts of Pakistan. During this process the plant become weaker or even dead due to destruction of phloem cells, the wounded places also become exposed to bacterial and fungal activities which become major cause of the plant death (Jamal & Huntsinger, 1993). The slow growing nature and commercially overexploitation the plant has become critically endangered throughout its habitats (Mishra and Kumar, 2010; Kulloli & Kumar 2013; Jain & Nadgauda, 2013).

Kund Malir is part of the Hingol National Park has great potential of *Commiphora wightii*. This valuable medicinal plant is being damaged either naturally or overexploiting by locals which is leading the plant to the verge of extinction, the plant exists in the dry habitat, produces less quantity of seeds, the chance of seed germination is also quite low (Ramawat, *et al.*, 1993), only little part of the plant seed can germinate, however the extensive grazing and longer droughts harshly reducing the regeneration rate. Presently, the area had a great cover of *Commiphora wightii* but since a few threats are liable to it so it will be soon extinct from the area if no conservation initiatives has been carried out. The purpose of the current study was to find out the presence and population status of this important and valuable but critically endangered plant species and its association with other species. The study also focused to identify existing threats within its natural habitat.

Material and Method:

Study Area: The word 'Kund Malir' has been derived from two Balochi words, 'Kund' means corner and 'Malir' as garden. The area under study and discussion lies at the western end of Lasbela district, about 170 km from Uthal city at latitude 25.395050 and longitude 65.463630 situated at the coastal part of Hingol National Park, the largest National Park of Balochistan and second largest in Pakistan. Soil is mostly sandy on the beach side but mostly gravelly and loamy sand to the steep mountainous sites with white clay cliffs. Weather of the spur and in the study area is humid and mostly mild ranging 15-30°C. Climate

is generally humid and it lies outside the sphere of monsoon. Rain fall is scanty, irregular, and sporadic, occurs in winter and occasionally in summer. The area is divided in number of villages and small settlement. Population of Kund Malir is spread over eleven (11) small villages with 30-40 households. The mountain system is a part of Makran Coastal Range and consists principally of barren ridges in the form of consecutive lines separated from one and other by narrow plains. Villages are located on both ends of the hills. The living system helps equal distribution of resources and providing spaces for livestock grazing, livelihood dependency of the people largely based on fishing, however, small scale rain fed agriculture is also practice in moisture containing furrows. Livestock includes sheep, cattle, goats, and camels rearing are another source of income.

Methodology: Line transects sampling method for studying plant communities in an area whereby a plant is sampled if transect line intersects the plant. The choice of the line interception method was made to measure cover, frequency, relative cover, relative frequency, density, Important Value Index and Sum Dominance Ratio of each plant species, the method is widely used for herbaceous and shrubby vegetation (Canfield, 1940; Shaukat *et al.*, 1976; Chul & Moody, 1983; Shukla & Srivastava, 1992; Smith and Smith, 1898). It is based primarily on the line transect; however, it incorporates a new technique for obtaining an inventory of the vegetation by line measurement of individual plants on a randomly selected sample. It appears to offer a practical, rapid and statistically sound means for sampling vegetation on both large and small range areas as well as on small plots used in detailed and intensive studies. Other species which was not covered under the transect line was observed at each sampled area and make an accumulative list for the species exists in the study areas. Garmin 12 Global Positioning System (GPS) and digital camera (Nikon AW110) were used in the study.

Results and Discussion: By using standard sampling method, total of eleven transects were taken randomly from different localities and calculate all parameters of *Commiphora wightii* and its associated plant species. T1 were placed at the sloppy step gravelly mountains where *Commiphora wightii* was found dominant among the other existing vegetation, regular drought made most of the associated herbaceous vegetation dry, the grass species like *Lasiurus* and *Saccharum* was heavily grazed, in the present situation the area was almost zero grazing capacity. *Commiphora* plant was found in fruiting stage which indicates high drought tolerance and resistance capacity of the species.

T2 was indicating comparatively diversified locality because of the furrows between mountains which remain moist for comparatively greater period, these types of micro-habitats having grazing potential for the larger period and have greater plant diversity. The locality observed with the dominant cover and frequency of *Commiphora*. Livestock and wild angulates such as Blandfort's Urial, Sindh Ibex, Chinkara Gazelles also use to graze *commiphora* fruits, therefore the plants cover and height remain deprived due to heavy grazing through domestic livestock such as goats and sheep as well as wild angulates. Total of then plants species recorded, 38.1% canopy covered by only *Commiphora* while the rest of 61.9 were shared by the remaining species that shows greater dominancy.

T3 were very low diversified area due to gravel and rocky terrain, only three species were associated to developed plant community, frequency of all three species was almost similar, *Indigofera oblongifolia* was more frequent among all three followed by *Commiphora wightii* and *Grewia tenax*, all these species are palatable both for domestic and wild angulates. All are facing severe drought, some individuals of *Prosopis juliflora* and *Ziziphus nummularia* was also serve as associated species and sharing habitat. The association of plants like *Prosopis juliflora* is also a serious concern for the

replacement of *Commiphora wightii* (Reddy et al., 2012).

T4: At this locality other species dominating over *Commiphora*, frequency and cover of *Commiphora* was lesser than the *Inula grantioides* and *Indigofera oblongifolia*, mix speciation reduce the chance of over-grazing and allow the plant to disperse its seed to maintain the population size, all of these three are palatable and provides good fodder to the wild angulates as well as domestic livestock.

T5: It is observed that the sloppy locations of the project sites generally dominating by *Commiphora wightii*, another species *Inula grantioides* shows dominancy side by side with the *Commiphora*. Other species recorded in the sampling sites was found very rarely such as *Fagonia indica*, *Grewia tenax*. Interestingly *Prosopis juliflora* was observed at and around every sampling site which indicates its invasion in the park area.

T6: The sample was taken from the rocky and sloppy area near the human settlement, significant cover has observed in the vicinity of the village. The sum dominance ratio indicates dominancy of the species followed by *Inula grantioides*, *Capparis decidua* and *Taverniera cuneifolia*.

T7: The sampling site was undulating and gravelly slop where *Commiphora* was dominant and uniformly scattered over the entire area, the species was looked like trimmed due to over grazing, the severe drought reduced the plant diversity of the entire study areas, wild angulates are very pron to *Commiphora*, a group of six Chinkara gazelles was observed to graze on the newly developed fruits of the *Commiphora*, this species play very productive role to provide compansation during drought months. Park management should focus on the development and protection of these spcies and have to developed some patches on installing solar based pumps and micro-irrigation (Sprinklings) to develop some patches inside the park during the drought years, these

steps not only provide compensation to the wild animals but also conserve the precious plant species like *Commiphora*.

T8: The sampled location was observed with significant density of *Prosopis juliflora* which replacing native species rapidly, due to its invasive behaviour it covers all the aspects and reducing chance for the growth of native species including *Commiphora*, it is observed that *Prosopis juliflora* has very deep root system which consume most of the underground water. This location still dominating by *Commiphora* with SDR value of 56% followed by *Cadaba heterotracha* with 23%, third dominant species was *Prosopis juliflora*. Few

individuals of *Aerva javanica* and *Periploca aphylla* was also scattered.

T9: A slightly furrowed area with comparatively high moisture contains and has the highest plant diversity among the rest of sampling sites, the dominant species was *Commiphora* followed by *Prosopis juliflora*.

T10 and T11: This site was the only sampling site where *Commiphora* was the second dominant species. Mostly the dominant species was grasses, such as *Lasiurus scindicus*. *Prosopis* was the third dominant plan. Greater diversity was observed at this locality.

Table 1: Shows % of Relative cover, frequency, density, important value index and sum dominance ratio

Transect No.	Coordinates	Locality	Species	R. C	R. F	R. D	IVI	SDR
1	25° 24' 30.30" N 65° 28' 43.61" E	Ghajan village	<i>Aerva javanica</i>	7	25	19	50.8	16.9
			<i>Commicarpus boissieri</i>	2.6	12.5	6.3	21.3	7.11
			<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	52	37.5	56	146	48.6
			<i>Prosopis Juliflora</i>	36	12.5	6.3	54.4	18.1
			<i>Seddera latifolia</i>	2.6	12.5	13	27.6	9.2
2	25° 24' 35.52" N 65° 28' 50.31" E	Ghajan village	<i>Asparagus dumosus</i>	4	6.7	6.9	18	5.85
			<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	59.8	20	34	114	38.1
			<i>Fagonia indica</i>	0.33	6.7	3.4	10	3.48
			<i>Grewia tenax</i>	5	6.7	10	22	7.34
			<i>Indigofera oblongifolia</i>	8.94	13	14	36	12
			<i>Inula grantioides</i>	0.39	6.7	3.4	11	3.5
			<i>Lycium edgeworthii</i>	9.61	6.7	3.4	20	6.57
			<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	1.72	6.7	3.4	12	3.95
			<i>Saccharum griffithii</i>	9.61	20	17	47	15.6
<i>Taverniera cuneifolia</i>	0.61	6.7	3.4	11	3.58			
3	25° 24' 00.08" N 65° 27' 43.87" E	Haji Washi village	<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	38.5	37.5	35.7	111.7	37.2
			<i>Grewia tenax</i>	5.41	25	14.3	44.69	14.9
			<i>Indigofera oblongifolia</i>	56.1	37.5	50	143.6	47.9
4	25° 24' 01.45" N 65° 27' 43.53" E	Sattar village	<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	0.28	30	20	50.3	16.8
			<i>Indigofera oblongifolia</i>	0.46	30	33.3	63.8	21.3
			<i>Inula grantioides</i>	0.55	30	40	70.6	23.5
			<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	0.18	9.91	13.3	23.4	7.81
5	25° 23' 58.42" N 65° 27' 44.81" E	Haji Amin village	<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	51	37.5	46.7	135.2	45.07
			<i>Fagonia indica</i>	1.07	12.5	6.67	20.24	6.746
			<i>Grewia tenax</i>	1.65	12.5	6.67	20.81	6.938
			<i>Inula grantioides</i>	40.6	37.5	40	118.1	39.35
			<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	5.69	12.4	6.67	24.73	8.243
6	25° 23' 56.54" N 65° 27' 47.59" E	Mir Abdullah village	<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	89	42.9	77.3	209.2	69.7
			<i>Inula grantioides</i>	5.2	28.6	13.6	47.43	15.8
			<i>Taverniera cuneifolia</i>	1.4	14.3	4.55	20.23	6.74

			<i>Capparis decidua</i>	4.3	14.3	4.55	23.12	7.71
7	25° 24' 00.63" N 65° 27' 53.39" E	Baadin village	<i>Aerva javanica</i>	4.07	12.5	8.3	24.9	8.3
			<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	68.4	37.5	50	156	52
			<i>Fagonia indica</i>	1.79	12.5	8.3	22.6	7.5
			<i>Indigofera oblongifolia</i>	12.7	12.5	8.3	33.5	11
8	25° 24' 02.24" N 65° 27' 59.82" E	Allah Buksh village	<i>Aerva javanica</i>	2.61	14.3	7.7	24.6	8.2
			<i>Cadaba heterotracha</i>	17.4	28.6	23	69	23
			<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	63.8	42.9	62	168	56
			<i>Periploca aphylla</i>	2.61	14.3	7.7	24.6	8.2
9	25° 25' 00.96' N 65° 29' 19.02" E	Umar village	<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	13.6	28.6	15	57.5	19
			<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	7.2	12.5	4.5	24.2	8.1
			<i>Capparis decidua</i>	1.4	25	1.4	27.7	9.2
			<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	94	37.5	94	225	75
			<i>Heliotropium crispum</i>	1.9	12.5	1.9	16.2	5.4
			<i>Pluchea arguta</i>	1	12.5	1	14.4	4.8
10	25° 25' 49.99" N 65° 30' 46.48" E	Lal Buksh village	<i>Saccharum griffithii</i>	2.2	12.5	2.2	16.9	5.6
			<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	7.6	25	7.6	40.2	13
			<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	35.4	20	16.7	72.1	24
			<i>Inula grantioides</i>	13.9	10	8.33	32.3	10.8
			<i>Lasiurus scindicus</i>	24.1	30	41.7	95.7	31.9
			<i>Nerium oleandar</i>	5.7	10	8.33	24	8.01
11	25° 23' 44.77" N 65° 27' 58.40" E	Yaqoob village	<i>Periploca aphylla</i>	15.8	20	16.7	52.5	17.5
			<i>Pluchea arguta</i>	5.06	10	8.33	23.4	7.8
			<i>Commiphora wightii</i>	28.8	20	16.7	65.4	21.8
			<i>Inula grantioides</i>	11.3	10	8.33	29.6	9.88
			<i>Lasiurus scindicus</i>	19.5	30	41.7	91.2	30.4
			<i>Nerium Oleandar</i>	4.62	10	8.33	23	7.65
			<i>Periploca aphylla</i>	12.8	20	16.7	49.5	16.5
			<i>Pluchea arguta</i>	4.11	10	8.33	22.4	7.48
			<i>Prosopis juliflora</i>	15.3	20	16.7	52	17.3

Figure 1 showing the meticulous picture of the entire project area where total of 11 samples was taken by using transect method, the transects were taken randomly in the entire project area where the actual species dominance has calculated with frequency, relative frequency, cover, related cover, important value index (IVI) and sum dominance ratio (SDR). Based on calculating figures *Commiphora wightii* was highly dominated species with the SDR value of 46.3 almost half of the

cover of the area's entire vegetation cover, identified during the assessment, the second dominated species with the SDR value of 12.3 was *Inula grantioides* which is belongs to family Asteraceae, the reason for their dominance was its strong aroma that prevent livestock and wild angulates from grazing, the third dominant species was *Prosopis juliflora* with the SDR value of 8.57, this species is a threat for the park's native vegetation.

Figure: 1, Showing Sum Dominance Ratio (SDR) ratio for the species of eleven sampling sites

The park has tremendous diversity of wildlife and natural flora, nearly 250 species of wild plants has been identified from the park area and has potential for more species existence. The number of species are quite high for the arid ecosystem

where persistent and prolong drought reducing chance of diversification. The study was conducted during the severe drought season, therefore, most of the annual herbs and grasses species was not observed.

Table 13: Shows total number of observed species for the study area

S.#	Species	Family	Local name
1.	<i>Acacia jacquemontii</i> Benth.	Mimosaceae	Chigerd
2.	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> (L.) Del.	Mimosaceae	Babur
3.	<i>Acacia senegal</i> (Linn.) Willd	Mimosaceae	Khor
4.	<i>Aerva javanica</i> (Burm.f.) Juss ex J.A. Schultes	Amaranthaceae	Gajoo
5.	<i>Asparagus dumosus</i> Baker	Asparagaceae	-
6.	<i>Cadaba heterotricha</i> Stocks ex Hooker	Capparidaceae	Jugar
7.	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Ait.) Ait.f.	Asclepiadaceae	Murpad
8.	<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forsk.) Edgew.	Capparidaceae	Kuler
9.	<i>Capparis cartilaginea</i> Decne.	Caparidaceae	Kirip
10.	<i>Capparis spinosa</i> L.	Capparidaceae	-
11.	<i>Commicarpus boissieri</i> (Heimerl) Cufod.	Nyctaginaceae	-
12.	<i>Commiphora wightii</i> (Arn.) Bhandari	Burseraceae	Guggl
13.	<i>Crotalaria burhia</i> Ham. Ex Bth.	Fabaceae	-
14.	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (Linn.) Pers.	Poaceae	-
15.	<i>Desmostachya bipinnata</i> (L.) Stapf	Poaceae	-
16.	<i>Fagonia indica</i> Burm.f.	Zygophyllaceae	Karkaho
17.	<i>Grewia tenax</i> (Forssk.) A. & S.	Tiliaceae	Guwangi
18.	<i>Heliotropium crispum</i> Desf.	Boraginaceae	-
19.	<i>Nerium oleander</i> Linn.	Apocynaceae	Johar
20.	<i>Indigofera oblongifolia</i> Forsk.	Fabaceae	-

21.	<i>Inula grantioides</i> Boiss	Asteraceae	Kolumoro
22.	<i>Lasiurus scindicus</i> Henr.	Poaceae	Booch
23.	<i>Lycium edgeworthii</i> Dunal	Solanaceae	Garathi/Kotor
24.	<i>Pluchea arguta</i> Boiss.	Asteraceae	Kinro
25.	<i>Prosopis juliflora</i> Swartz	Mimosaceae	Devi
26.	<i>Saccharum griffithii</i> Munro ex Boiss.	Poaceae	Korh/Keesh
27.	<i>Seddera latifolia</i> Hochst. & Steud.	Convolvulaceae	-
28.	<i>Salsola imbricata</i> Forssk	Chenopodiaceae	Kanrak
29.	<i>Suaeda fruticosa</i> Forsk. Ex J.F. Gmelin	Chenopodiaceae	Mesik
30.	<i>Tamarix aphylla</i> (L.) H.Karst.	Tamaricaceae	Gazz
31.	<i>Taverniera cuneifolia</i> (Roth.) Arnott	Fabaceae	Jethmad
32.	<i>Ziziphus nummularia</i> (Burm.f.) Wight & Arn.	Rhamnaceae	Ber
33.	<i>Mongifera indica</i> (Cultivated)	Anacardiaceae	Aam
34.	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce	Mimosaceae	Kahoor
35.	<i>Periploca aphylla</i> Decne.	Asclepiadaceae	Geeshtar

Conclusion: The study indicates a strong presence of *Commiphora wightii* in the area, accounting for 46% of the total biomass. This is followed by *Inula grantioides* at 12% and *Prosopis juliflora* at 8%. Historically, the landscape supported an even greater abundance of *C. wightii*, a key species valued for its high guggulsterone content. However, its population has been steadily declining due to heavy grazing pressure, recurring droughts, inherently slow growth, low seed germination rates, unsustainable resin-tapping practices, and the spread of invasive species. In line with the national park's management plan, urgent in situ conservation measures are essential to safeguard this rare and medicinally important plant before its loss becomes irreversible.

Acknowledgement: The authors express their gratitude to the park management for their guidance and support throughout the study. Special appreciation is extended to Master Abdul Rehman, local activist and General Secretary of the Village Conservation Committee, Kund Malir, for his valuable assistance.

REFERENCES:

- Abbas, F. A., S. M. Al-Massarany, S. Khan, T. A. Al-Howiriny, J. S. Mossa and E. A. Abourashed (2007). Photochemical and biological studies on Saudi *Commiphora opobalsamum* L. Nat. Prod. Res. 21:383-391.
- Allam, A. F., M. H. El-Sayed and S. S. Kahlil (2001). Laboratory assessment of molluscicidal activity of *Commiphora molmol* (myrrha) on *Biomphalaria alexandrina*, *Bulinus truncates* and *Lymnea cailliaudi*. J. Egypt Soc. Parasitol. 31:683-690.
- Antherosclerosis 172:239-246.
- Aral, C. K., O. P. Gupta, S. H. Afaq (1975). *Commiphora mukul*: source of Guggal in Indian systems of medicine. Economic Bot. 29:208-218.
- Canfield, R. H. (1940). Application of line interception method in sampling range vegetation. Jour. For. 23:388-394.
- Chakravarty, H. L. (1975). Herbal heritage of India. Bull. Bot. Soc. Bengal 29:97-103.
- Choudhary, I. I. (1959). Scope of plant introduction in agriculture and forestry of West Pakistan. Pak. J. Fore. 9:208-211.
- Chul, K. S. and K. Moody (1983). Comparison of some methodologies for vegetation analysis in transplanted rice. Korean J. Crop. Sci. 28(3):310-318.

- Claeson, P., R. Anderson and G. Samuelson (1991). T-cadinol: a pharmacologically active constituent of scented myrrha: introductory pharmacological characterization and high field ¹H and ¹³C-NMR data. *Planta Med.* 57:352-356.
- Francis, J. A., S. N. Raja and M. G. Nair (2004). Bioactive terpenoids and guggulosteroid from *Commiphora mukul* gum resin of potential antiinflammatory interest. *Chem. Biodivers.* 1:1842-53.
- Goyal, C., M. Ahuja and S. Sharma (2011). Preparation and evaluation of antiinflammatory activity of gugalipid-loaded proniosomal gel. *Acta Pol. Pharm. Drug Res.* 68:147-150.
- Gupta, P., K. R. Shivanna and R. H. Y. Mohan (1996). Apomixis and Polyembryony in the Guggal Plant. *Ann. Bot.* 78:67-72.
- Hanus, O., T. Rezankab, V. M. Dembitsky and A. Moussaieff (2005). Myrrh-*Commiphora* chemistry. *Biomed Papers* 149:3-28.
- Hocking, D. (1993). *Trees for Drylands*. Oxford and IBH Publishing Co, New Delhi.
- Hooker, J. D. (1872). *The Flora of British India*. Part-I London: Reeve, P. 740.
- Jafri, S. M. H. (1966). *The Flora of Karachi*, the Book Corporation, Karachi, Pakistan.
- Jain, N & R. S. Nadgauda (2013). *Commiphora wightii* (Arnott) Bhandari—A Natural Source of Guggulsterone: Facing a High Risk of Extinction in Its Natural Habitat. *American Journal of Plant Sciences*, 4, 57-68.
- Jamal, A., and L. Huntsinger (1993). Deterioration of a sustainable agro-silvopastoral system in the Sudan: the gum gardens of Kordofan. *Agroforestry Syst.* 23:23-28.
- Joshi, A. (1980). *Ayurvedic Patrikaritaka has* (History of Ayurvedic Publications). Mimeo. Mohan Ayurvedic Pharmacy Jodhpur, India p 260.
- Kant, T., S. Prajapati and A. Parmar (2010). Efficient micropropagation from cotyledonary node cultures of *Commiphora wightii* (Arn.) Bhandari, an endangered medicinally important desert plant. *J. Plant Dev.* 17:37-48.
- Khan, A. H. (1958). The essential oil bearing plants of Pakistan part -1. *Pak. J. For.* 8(3):262-283.
- Kulloli, R. N. & S. Kumar (2013). *Commiphora wightii* (Arnott) Bhandari: A threatened plant of conservation concern. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*. Vol. 7(28), pp. 2043-2052.
- Kumar, S. and V. Shankar (1982). Medicinal plants of the Indian desert: *Commiphora wightii* (Arnott) Band. *J. Arid Environ.* 5:1-11.
- Massoud, A. M., F. H. E. I. Ebiary, E. I. Abd and N. F. Salam (2004). Effect of myrrha extract on the liver of normal and bilhazially infected mice. An ultrastructural study. *J. Egypt Soc. Parasitol.* 34:1-21.
- Massoud, A. M., I. M. Labib and M. Rady (2001). Biochemical changes of *Culex pipiens* larvae treated with oil and oleo-resin extracts of myrrha, *Commiphora molmol*. *J. Egypt Soc. Parasitol.* 31:517-29.
- Mishra, S. K. and A. Kumar (2010). Biosynthesis of guggulsterone in the callus culture of *Commiphora wightii*. Arnott. bhandari (Bursaceae). *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*. Vol. 1 (3) p. 35.
- Nasir, E. and S. I. Ali (Eds.). (1972). *Bursaceae*. *Flora of Pakistan* Vol. 26.
- Ramawat, K. G., D. Nandwani, N. Mathur & K. C. Sonie (1993). *Tree Biol Himalayan Trop Species*, pp. 99-102.
- Reddy, C. S., S. L. Meena, P. H. Krishna, P. D. Charan and K. C. Sharma (2012). Conservation Threat Assessment of *Commiphora wightii* (Arn.) Bhandari—An Economically Important Species. *Taiwania*, Vol. 57, No. 3, pp. 288-293.

- Satyavati, G. V. (1990). Guggulipid: a promising hypolipidemic agent from gum guggul (*Commiphora wightii*) Econ. Med. Plant 5:47-82.
- Shaukat, S. S., A. Khairi and R. Ahmad (1976). A Phytosociological study of Gadap area, southern Sind, Pakistan. Pak. J. Bot. 8(2): 133-149.
- Shen, T., W. Wan, H. Yuan, F. Kong, H. Guo, P. Fan and H. Lou (2007). Secondary metabolites from *Commiphora opobalsamum* and their anti-proliferative effect on human prostrate cancer cells. Phytochemistry 68:1331-1337.
- Shukla, S. K. and P. K. Srivastava (1992). Environmental Wildlife Impact Analysis. Commonwealth Publisher, New Delhi, India.
- Smith, R. L. and T. M. Smith (1998). Elements of ecology. Addison Wesley Longman, Inc. Pp:269-278.
- Soni, V. (2010). Efficiency of in vitro tissue culture versus stem cuttings for propagation of *Commiphora wightii* in Rajasthan. India Conserv. Evid. 7:91-93.
- Thulin, M. (2000). Ten new species of *Commiphora* (Burseraceae) from Somalia. Nord. J. Bot. 20:395-411.
- Vander Walt, J. J. A. (1974). A preliminary report on the genus *Commiphora* in South-west Africa. Madoqua 1(8):5-23.
- Vander Walt, J. J. A. (1975). The south west African species of *Commiphora*. Mitteilungen der Botanischen Staatssammlung Muenchea 12:195-266.
- Vollesen, K. (1989). Burseraceae. In: Hedberg, I., Edwards, S. (Eds.), Flora of Ethiopia. The National Herbarium—Addis Ababa University and The Department of Systematic Botany—Uppsala University, Addis Ababa, Ethiopia pp. 442-478.
- Wang X., J. Greilber, G. Ledinski, G. Kager, B. Paigen and G. Juergen (2004). The hypolipidemic natural product *Commiphora mukul* and its component guggulusterone inhibit oxidative modification of LDL.